

Comparison of the Relative Physicochemical Role of Parent, Proximate and Ultimate Carcinogenic Forms of Aromatic Amines : A Semiempirical Molecular Orbital Study

JAYATI SENGUPTA^{a*} and R. H. DUNCAN LYNGDOH^b

^aInstitute of Self Organising System and Biophysics, North-Eastern Hill University, Mawlai, Shillong-793 022

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 003

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It is widely believed that *N*-hydroxylation of the parent aromatic amines is the key activation pathway for carcinogenesis, leading to formation of ultimate carcinogen via arylhydroxamic acids as proximate carcinogen. The candidate ultimate carcinogens for aromatic amines are the electrophilic arylnitrenium ions. Using semiempirical SCF-MO theory, the experimental results have been corroborated by the trends consistently predicted from theoretical indices.

Aromatic compounds that have nitrogen atoms attached to their ring carbons (Fig. 1) have a potential for eliciting a variety of mutagenic and carcinogenic responses^{1,2}. The investigation of tumor induction in animals by the aromatic

Fig. 1. Aromatic amines studied: 1-naphthyl amine (1), 2-naphthyl amine (2), 4-aminobiphenyl (3), benzidine (4), 2-acetylaminofluorene (5), 2-aminofluorene (6), 3-acetylaminofluorene (7) and 3-aminofluorene (8).

amines helped to confirm the epidemiological conclusion and provide experimental models for human bladder cancer³. Unlike the direct acting carcinogens, all aromatic amines require metabolic activation into a strong electrophilic reactant to be able to bind chemically to nucleophilic sites in the target cells⁴. Aromatic amines do not induce tumors at the site of their administration but usually at a distance site, such as the liver, intestine or urinary bladder. There are great differences among these agents in species and tissue susceptibilities to cancer induction due

to the differences in the metabolism of aromatic amines. Most of the metabolites are excreted as either sulphate or glucuronide conjugates, all serving as proximate carcinogens for further metabolism to electrophilic ultimate carcinogenic form, e.g. *N*-hydroxylation of 2-naphthylamine leads to a reactive product that is transported to the bladder as the *N*-glucuronide, which is itself unstable at low pH value and are thought to act as proximate bladder carcinogen through release of *N*-hydroxy compound at the acidic pH of urine¹.

N-Hydroxylation is considered to be the initial activation step in carcinogenesis, whereas hydroxylation of the aromatic rings appears to provide a detoxification pathway⁶ (Fig. 2). The details of metabolic activation have been worked out primarily with a potent hepatocarcinogen 2-acetylaminofluorene⁶. *N*-Oxidation of all these compounds led to the formation of arylhydroxamic acids as proximate carcinogen. These reactions are catalysed by the cyto-

Fig. 2. Metabolic activation and deactivation pathways for aromatic amines.

chrome p-450 dependent monooxygenase systems. The hydroxylating cytochrome p-450 enzyme system, through its triplet oxygen in the heme moiety, abstracts a hydrogen atom and replaces it with a hydroxyl radical. *N*-Hydroxy derivatives of aromatic amines require further metabolism to form the electrophilic reactant, i.e. the ultimate carcinogen⁷. The candidate ultimate carcinogens for aromatic amines are the electrophilic aryl nitrenium ions⁸.

One route of activation for aryl hydroxamic acids is by peroxidase and H₂O₂, which form a free radical from the *N*-hydroxyamine⁹. Theoretical calculation has been done on activation of ArNH₂ and interaction with DNA bases. Loew *et al.*¹⁰ studied some aromatic amines and their nitrenium ions using semiempirical methods (IEHT, PCILO, INDO). They also studied the interaction of naphthyl amine with C-8 guanine. *Ab initio* and semiempirical calculations at the MNDO and AM1 level have been done extensively on nitrenium ions to predict their preferential stability, relation to mutagenicity and substituent effects on stabilities¹¹. The reliability of MNDO method has been established by systematic comparison with experimental data so that mean absolute errors are available for many ground state properties¹². The strength of MOPAC lies in its ability to provide accurate values of molecular properties from relatively fast calculations on medium to large molecules at about a fifth of the cost of *ab initio* methods. Electrophilic reactivity of parent aromatic amines, *N*-hydroxylated forms (proximate carcinogen) and nitrenium ions (ultimate carcinogen) have been calculated and compared using MNDO SCF-MO method. Electrophilicity at two sites, viz. at the nitrogen of nitrenium moiety as well as the carbon in closest conjugation to this, is exhibited.

Free radical reactions occur widely in various types of cell injury¹³ and under certain controlled conditions, as part of normal metabolism. Highly reactive free radicals, such as OH[•]¹⁴ have correspondingly small radii of diffusion and they may interact with aromatic amine metabolites. A comparison is shown here for the ease of formation of radicals (N- and C-) and nitrenium ions.

Method of calculations :

The wavefunctions for all molecular species studied were calculated in the MNDO approximation^{12,15} using MOPAC package¹⁶. Geometries were optimised with no constraints for parent amines, *N*-hydroxylated forms, nitrenium ions and N-, C-radicals of each amine by DFP method¹⁷. Trial geometries were constructed from standard bond lengths and bond angles¹⁸.

Frontier MO interaction term : T_h and T_1 (eqns. 1 and 2) could serve as indices for estimating the extent of frontier MO interaction taking place between the hydrogen and the triplet oxygen of the enzyme,

$$T_h = C_h^2 / E_p - E_h \quad (1)$$

$$T_1 = C_1^2 / E_1 - E_p \quad (2)$$

where C_h , E_h and C_1 , E_1 are the coefficient and energy of HOMO and LUMO respectively, involving the hydrogens and E_p is the energy of the SOMO (singly occupied MO) of triplet oxygen,

$$T_{xh} = T_h + T_1 \quad (3)$$

Indices concerning electrophilicity :

Charge on relevant atoms (Q), interaction term (T) is expressed by the equation,

$$T = \sum C_{\text{lumo}}^2 / E_{\text{lumo}} - E_{\text{homo}}^G \quad (4)$$

where E_{homo}^G is the highest occupied molecular orbital of base guanine, and C_{lumo} and E_{lumo} are the coefficient and energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital of the relevant atom.

Indices concerning stability : Calculated enthalpies (ΔH) of the formal reaction process shown in equations (5-7) relate to the energies of *N*-hydroxylation and nitrenium ion formation,

These thermodynamic criteria determine the extent to which the nitrenium ion formation would compete with other reactions.

Index for bond strength : The strength of the bond may be measured by the Wiberg bond index¹⁹ (W_{ab}), where, for any bond between atoms A and B equation (8) holds,

$$W_{ab} = \frac{A \ B}{\sum_m \sum_n} P_{mn}^2 \quad (8)$$

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents a comparison of the MNDO calculated values for the indices concerning hydroxylation by triplet oxygen. In the competition between N- and C-hydroxylation pathways in the parent amines, the former was found to be definitely favoured. Tables 2 and 3 compare the electrophilic reactivity among the parent, the proximate and the ultimate carcinogen species. Results show that the electrophilicity of ultimate carcinogens, the nitrenium ions, is much greater than the other two species. The electrophilicity was studied in two sites, viz. N- (of nitrenium, Table 2) and C- (adjacent to nitrenium moiety, Table 3) sites (Fig. 3). Results show that the electrophilicity of the C-site is more than the N-site, revealing the soft character of the N-site²⁰.

The quantities ΔH , correspond to the calculated enthalpies of the formal reaction processes shown in equations

TABLE 1—MINDO CALCULATED INDICES FOR N AND C HYDROXYLATION OF PARENT AROMATIC AMINES USING TRIPLET OXYGEN MODEL (T IN a.u.)

Compd.	W_{nh}	T_{nh}	Q_{nh}	W_{ch}	T_{ch}	Q_{ch}
1NA	0.955	0.542	0.111	0.963	0.191	0.060
2NA	0.956	0.520	0.114	0.963	0.189	0.061
4AB	0.958	0.821	0.115	0.962	0.187	0.064
BZ	0.959	0.541	0.114	0.963	0.124	0.063
AF(2)	0.959	1.323	0.115	0.963	1.023	0.062
AAF(2)	0.936	1.306	0.149	0.962	1.020	0.103
AF(3)	0.959	1.266	0.114	0.963	0.142	0.062
AAF(3)	0.936	1.294	0.149	0.962	1.046	0.103

Fig. 3. Nitrenium ions (ultimate carcinogenic form) (A) and their imine forms (B) for different aromatic amines.

 TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF N-ATOM ELECTROPHILICITY OF PARENT, PROXIMATE AND ULTIMATE CARCINOGENS OF DIFFERENT AROMATIC AMINES (T_N IN a.u.)

Compd.	$ArNH_2$		$ArNHOH$		$ArNH^+$	
	Q_N	T_N	Q_N	T_N	Q_N	T_N
1NA	-0.230	0.260	-0.114	0.627	-0.074	1.451
2NA	-0.229	0.284	-0.110	0.351	-0.033	1.902
4AB	-0.230	0.308	-0.078	0.714	-0.046	1.640
BZ	-0.229	0.188	-0.108	0.655	-0.090	0.791
AF(2)	-0.230	0.208	-0.078	0.535	-0.063	1.260
AAF(2)	-0.336	0.162	-0.221	0.581	-0.164	2.307
AF(3)	-0.229	0.196	-0.080	0.392	-0.024	2.507
AAF(3)	-0.333	0.193	-0.232	0.443	-0.160	2.388

(5, 6) would be expected to contribute towards the experimentally observed trend. The enzymatic hydroxylation route for generation of the ultimate carcinogen (ΔH_o) was compared (Table 4) with the alternative transformation route of hydride ion loss (ΔH_h), and the former was found to be definitely to be the more favoured one energetically (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Plots of calculated (MINDO) relative activation enthalpies for different pathways : (---) equation (5) and (—) equation (6).

 TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF C-ATOM ELECTROPHILICITY OF PARENT, PROXIMATE AND ULTIMATE CARCINOGENS OF DIFFERENT AROMATIC AMINES (T_C IN a.u.)

Compd.	$ArNH_2$		$ArNHOH$		$ArNH^+$	
	Q_C	T_C	Q_C	T_C	Q_C	T_C
1NA	-0.107	0.308	-0.048	0.362	0.198	2.778
2NA	-0.089	0.450	-0.066	0.452	0.188	4.235
4AB	-0.098	0.600	-0.046	0.481	0.153	1.401
BZ	-0.099	0.433	-0.060	0.482	0.103	1.398
AF(2)	-0.043	0.539	-0.034	0.542	0.153	1.144
AAF(2)	-0.088	0.586	-0.022	0.567	0.161	1.338
AF(3)	-0.097	0.573	-0.073	0.494	0.207	3.571
AAF(3)	-0.087	0.657	-0.066	0.522	0.189	3.782

 TABLE 4—ENTHALPIES OF FORMAL REACTION PROCESSES (EQNS. 5-7) FOR DIFFERENT PATHWAYS OF ARYLNITRENIUM IONS FORMATION (ΔH IN kcal)

Compd.	ΔH_o	ΔH_h	ΔH_i
1NA	138.57	277.72	-40.39
2NA	145.36	276.68	-34.51
4AB	145.00	284.15	-37.36
BZ	137.06	276.21	-42.82
AF(2)	138.31	277.46	-45.93
AAF(2)	143.43	282.18	-35.33
AF(3)	147.30	286.45	-37.04
AAF(3)	142.49	281.64	-32.19

Also, the estimated values of enthalpy of the reaction process shown by equation (7) (Table 4), reveal the stability of the nitrenium ions. Thermodynamics of the formation of radicals, N- (amine group) as well as C- (most reactive carbon, in closest conjugation to the amine), employing triplet oxygen model, is shown in the Table 5 to focus a different route of activation of aromatic amines.

Conclusion : The results indicate a marked difference among the species. On the basis of reactivity criteria for single atom and bond obtained from molecular orbital calculations it has been shown that the aryl nitrenium ion metabolites are definitely much more electrophilic than their parent counterparts and also exhibit this electrophilicity at

two sites. The relative inertness of the parent amine thus predicted hence predicts the necessity of its conversion to a more electrophilic species *in vivo* if DNA modification is to be effected.

TABLE 5—ENTHALPIES OF PRODUCTION OF N AND C RADICALS FROM THE PARENT AROMATIC AMINES (ΔH IN kcal)

Compd.	ΔH_N	ΔH_C
1NA	-47.08	-20.16
2NA	-45.35	-10.37
4AB	-42.19	-16.28
BZ	-42.46	-16.50
AF(2)	-45.55	-19.19
AAF(2)	-52.40	-22.84
AF(3)	-42.02	-18.87
AAF(3)	-51.24	-21.94

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References

1. R. C. GARNER, C. N. MARTIN and D. B. CLAYSON in "Chemical Carcinogenesis", ed. C. E. SEARLE, ACS Monograph 182, Am Chem. Soc., Washington DC, 1982, p.175.
2. B. SINGER and D. GRUNBERGER, "Molecular of Carcinogens and Mutagens", Plenum, New York, 1983.
3. W. C. HUEPER, F. H. WILEY and H. D. WOLFE, *J. Ind. Hyg.*, 1938, **20**, 46; F. F. KADLUBAR, J. A. MILLER and E. C. MILLER, *Cancer Res.*, 1977, **37**, 805.
4. J. A. MILLER, *Cancer Res.*, 1970, **30**, 559.
5. E. C. MILLER, P. D. LOTLIKAR, H. C. PITOT, T. L. FLETCHER and J. A. MILLER, *Cancer Res.*, 1966, **26**, 2239; G. J. HAMMONS, F. P. GUENGESICH, C. C. WEIS, F. A. BELAND and F. F. KADLUBAR, *Cancer Res.*, 1985, **45**, 3578.
6. S. S. THORGEIRSSON, P. J. WIRTH, N. STAIANO and C. L. SMITH, *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.*, 1982, **136B**, 897.
7. P. D. LOTLIKAR, J. D. SCRIBNER, J. A. MILLER and E. C. MILLER, *Life Sci.*, 1966, **5**, 1263.
8. S. S. THORGEIRSSON, I. B. GLOWINSKI and M. E. MCMANUS, *Rev. Biochem. Toxicol.*, 1983, **5**, 349; E. KRICK and J. G. WESTRA in "Chemical Carcinogenesis and DNA", ed. P. L. GROVER, CRC Press, Boca Raton 1979. Vol. II; F. F. KADLUBAR and F. A. BELAND in "Polycyclic Hydrocarbons and Carcinogenesis", ed. R. G. HARVEY, Am. Chem. Soc., Washington DC, 1985, p. 341.
9. H. BARTSCH and E. HECKER, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta.* 1971, **237**, 567.
10. G. LOEW, B. S. SUDHINDRA, S. B. RT and G. R. PACK, *Int J Quantum Chem. Quantum Biol. Symp.*, 1979, **6**, 259.
11. G. P. FORD and J. D. SCRIBNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 4281; G. P. FORD and P. S. HERMAN, *J. Mol. St.*, 1991, **236**, 269; 1990, **204**, 121; *Chem. Biol. Interact.*, 1992, **81**, 1.
12. M. J. S. DEWAR and W. THIEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 4907.
13. T. F. SLATER, "Free Radical Mechanisms in Tissue Injury", Pion, London, 1972.
14. T. F. SLATER, *Pan Minerva Medica*, 1976, **18**, 381.
15. M. J. S. DEWAR and W. THIEL, *J. Am Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 4899.
16. J. J. P. STEWART, *QCPE Bull.*, 1983, **3**, 43.
17. R. FLETCHER and M. J. D. POWELL, *Comput. J.*, 1963, **6**, 163; W. DEVIDON, *Comput. J.*, 1968, **10**, 406.
18. J. A. POPLER and D. L. BEVERIDGE, "Approximate Molecular Orbital Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1970, p.111.
19. K. B. WIBERG, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 1083.
20. R. G. PEARSON, *Science*, 1966, **151**, 172.